

Research of running performance of new generation river-sea passenger vessel

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Abstract. The paper is intended for Advancements in design methodology conference and is devoted to prediction of towing resistance of river-sea passenger vessels.

The new generation of river-sea cruise passenger vessels (PV) are characterized by new approaches to their design and the use of modern forms of ship's contours, which are caused by usage of advanced propulsion systems. These features of the new generation passenger ships make it difficult to apply statistical methods for determining towing resistance taking into consideration appearance of non-traditional aft hull contours.

Therefore, the results of calculations using statistical methods or determination of resistance using CFD methods need to be verified by conducting model tests. Physical modelling of the movement of new generation passenger vessel in the research basin of Odesa National Marine University on calm deep water and in regular waves was carried out.

Experimental data of the running qualities of the new generation river-sea passenger vessel's model was achieved. Design solutions for determining the towing resistance and required towing power were confirmed. The vessel's sea-keeping performance in regular waves was investigated; the coefficients of additional resistance in regular waves were determined. The data obtained can be used in the future for the development design for similar vessels.

Keywords: *Cruise passenger vessel, river-sea vessels, hull forms, running properties, propulsion system, model tests, additional resistance in regular waves.*

Introduction

Problem statement. The new generation of river-sea cruise passenger vessels (PV) differs significantly from classic river and modernized to mixed class cruise passenger vessels both in terms of their technical equipment and conceptually; other approaches have been applied to determining the main dimensions, contours, assessing running qualities, forming passenger and public spaces [1-6].

Time has changed the shape of PV hull, the main dimensions ratio, and the propulsion system's type. This paper describes results of an attempt of experimental evaluation the features of new type hull shapes for prospective river-sea PV.

The application of the principle of maximum usage of the dimensions of inland waterways for which the vessel is designed, as well as the introduction of new propulsion complexes (rudder propellers and azimuthal units [7-9], wheeled propulsion units [10]) by analogy with cargo vessels [11], led to the need to create new effective hull contours. At the same time, the hull contours themselves are created and optimized by the software complexes that simply did not exist at the time of designing the currently available PV. The performance of such calculations is accompanied by verification of the results of numerical modelling through physical modelling at test towing tanks.

The purpose of the paper is to study the running qualities of a new generation passenger vessel developed by the Marine Engineering Bureau. During the study, an experimental determination of the towing resistance and towing power of the vessel was carried out for sailing at sea in deep water both for conditions of calm water and regular waves.

1. Main material

As it was noted in [3], the most suitable is the traditional single-hull type of PV for operating conditions of the Southern European region and Black Sea – Caspian region. The design of a new generation single-hull passenger vessel PV140 was considered as the object of the study.

PV of the PV140 project is a steel self-propelled vessel with sloping bow and transom stern, with excess freeboard; with 4-tier living superstructure along the while vessel's length that includes poop and enlarged forecabin; with wheelhouse located fore and engine room located aft. Three full-turn rudder propellers are used as propulsion units.

Side view of the new generation PV of the PV140 project is shown in the Figure 1; body lines of the PV140 project is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Side view of the PV140 project.

Figure 2. Lines of the PV140 project.

The test was conducted in the towing tank of the Odessa National Maritime University (ONMU) in calm deep water and regular waves.

The PV characteristics are given in the Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of the Object of the study (PV140 passenger vessel) and its model

<i>Item</i>		<i>Model</i>	<i>Vessel</i>
Length between perpendiculars, m	L_{bp}	2.947	140.00
Length due to waterline, m	L_{wl}	2.968	141.00
Breadth, m	B	0.349	16.60
Draught, m	d	0.063	3.00
Block coefficient	C_B	0.814	
Displacement volumetric, m ³	∇	0.0534	5718.60
Displacement, t	Δ	0.055	5861.57
Wetted surface area, m ²	S	1.207	2724.00
Model scale	-	1:47.5	
Roughness increment	C_A	-	0.00035
Protrusion (outer parts) factor	-	-	1.020
Water temperature in the tank, °C	t	13.0	-
Sea water temperature, °C	t_H	-	4
Density of sea water, kgf s ² /m ⁴	ρ	-	103.2
Water depth in the tank	H/d	deep water	

The PV140 model was made in 1:47.5 scale using the standard ONMU towing tank's technology; the model material was foam plastic coated by an alloy of wax and paraffin. Since the model has an L/B ratio close to 8.5, its hull is reinforced with longitudinal stiffeners made of plywood. The view of the aft end of the model is shown in the Figure 3, the view of the fore end of the model is shown in the Figure 4. The general view of the PV model is given in the Figure 5; the Figure 6 shows the floating model before being hitched to the towing system.

Figure 3. Aft end and bottom of the PV model.

Figure 4. Turbulators installed, view from fore.

Figure 5. General view of the PV model.

Figure 6. Model before hitching to tow system.

2. Test program

The ONMU towing tank has historically older Vellenkamp-type towing system with ropes and gravity towing system that involves setting the towing force instead of setting the velocity as in historically newer dynamometer-type towing tanks. When carrying out towing tests, in accordance with the methodology for conducting such tests at gravity towing tanks, the model is repeatedly run to determine the required acceleration cargo weight and confirm the movement stability (on average about 10 runs); then single final measurement run is carried out.

PV under consideration is of mixed river-sea type, which reflects its class. The selected wavelength/PV length ratios correspond to typical wavelengths for the northern and north-western parts of the Black Sea, where marine operation of this project PV is expected.

2.1. Test program in calm water

Towing tests were carried out for model's draught of 0.063 m (3.00 m for full scale vessel) in ahead motion according to the methodology [19] approved by the ONMU, in the range of the PV model speeds corresponding to Froude numbers $Fr = 0.098 \div 0.183$ (by step corresponding to the model resistance of 0.20 ÷ 0.30 kgf).

2.2. Towing tests in calm deep water

Towing tests in calm deep water were carried out for the case of the largest draught, which corresponds to the conditions of marine navigation. The results of the towing tests of the model are given below (see Figures 16 and 17). During movement at low speeds wave formation was moderate; during movement at medium speeds wave formation at the fore edge increased, a distinct running wave appeared (see Figures 7 and 8); this running wave became significant at maximum speed movement. The results of the towing tests were recalculated to full scale, Figures 18 and 19 demonstrate the dependence of the towing resistance and towing power on the speed respectively.

Figure 7. Towing of the model in deep water at medium speed, $Fr = 0.145$.

Figure 8. Towing of the model in deep water at speeds close to calculated value, $Fr = 0.183$.

2.3. Regular wave test program

Towing tests of the model were conducted in regular oncoming waves in deep water with the model characteristics specified in Table 1.

The characteristics of regular waves are given in Table 2. In this case, the relative steepness of regular waves is taken as $h/\lambda = 1/30$. The selected wave steepness takes into account both the wave generation capabilities of the wave generation installed in the ONMU towing tank and the parameters of real waves that the vessel may encounter in operation.

The plate wave producer of the ONMU towing tank generates waves with a near-sinusoidal profile, with the main characteristics of the deep water wave (except for the height h) being functions of the wavelength λ . String digital wave height sensors of original design [19;20] are used to fit the wave characteristics.

Towing tests in regular waves were conducted for the case of the largest draught, which corresponds to the marine navigation conditions.

The results of the towing tests of the model are given below (see Figures 16 and 17).

During movement at low speeds wave formation was moderate; during movement at medium speeds an increase in wave formation was observed at the fore edge, a distinct running wave appeared (see the Figures 9, 11, 13 and 15), which became significant at movement at speed close to the design one (see the Figures 10, 12, 14); the same time intensive flooding at the fore edge was observed.

Figure 9. Towing of the model in deep water by medium speeds, $Fr = 0.159$. Regular waves $\lambda/L = 0.25$.

Figure 10. Towing of the model in deep water by speed close to the design one, $Fr = 0.185$. Regular waves $\lambda/L = 0.25$.

Figure 11. Towing of the model in deep water by medium speeds, $Fr = 0.152$. Regular waves $\lambda/L = 0.50$.

Figure 12. Towing of the model in deep water by speed close to the design one, $Fr = 0.180$. Regular waves $\lambda/L = 0.50$.

Figure 13. Towing of the model in deep water by medium speeds, $Fr = 0.126$. Regular waves $\lambda/L = 0.625$.

Figure 14. Towing of the model in deep water by speed close to the design one, $Fr = 0.168$. Regular waves $\lambda/L = 0.625$.

Figure 15. Towing of the model in deep water by medium speeds, $Fr = 0.147$. Regular waves $\lambda/L = 0.75$.

Table 2. Regular waves characteristics

λ/L	Model						Vessel	
	Wave length	Wave number $k = 2\pi/\lambda$	Wave frequency $\sigma = \sqrt{gk}$	Wave period $\tau = 2\pi/\sigma$	Wave generator frequency	Wave height	Wave height	Wave length
	λ	k	σ	τ	σ_{wg}	h	h	λ
	m	-	1/s	s	Hz	mm	m	m
0.250	0.742	8.467	9.112	0.690	53.66	24.74	1.175	35.25
0.500	1.484	4.233	6.443	0.975	37.94	49.47	2.350	70.50
0.625	1.855	3.387	5.763	1.090	33.94	61.84	2.938	88.13
0.750	2.226	2.822	5.261	1.194	30.98	74.21	3.525	105.75

Figure 16. Towing resistance of the PV model in calm water.

Figure 17. Towing resistance of the PV model in regular waves.

Figure 18. Vessel's towing resistance.

Figure 19. Vessel's towing power.

The additional resistance coefficient for regular waves C_{aw} is defined using the residual resistance coefficient of a vessel in calm water $C_{r_{cw}}(Fr)$:

$$C_{aw} = C_r - C_{r_{cw}}(Fr)$$

The value of the residual resistance coefficient of a vessel in calm water $C_{r_{cw}}(Fr)$ is determined by nonlinear interpolation.

The calculation results are given in the Table 3. The dependences of the residual resistance coefficient of a vessel in calm water $C_{r_{cw}}(Fr)$ for selected wave characteristics are given in the Figure 20. The dependences of the additional resistance coefficient for regular waves $C_{aw}(Fr)$ for selected wave characteristics are given in the Figure 21.

Figure 20. Dependences of the total residual resistance coefficient in regular waves C_r on the relative speed of a vessel.

Figure 21. Dependences of the additional resistance coefficient in regular waves C_{aw} on the relative speed of a vessel.

Figures 20 and 21 show that in regular waves with small values of λ/L (0.25; 0.50 - short waves) the model did not have time to accelerate enough. Whereas on medium and long waves ($\lambda/L = 0.625$; 0.75), motion with Froude numbers greater than 0.17 was unattainable due to the intense interaction between the wave and the model (see Figure 15).

Figure 22. Dependences of the additional resistance coefficient in regular waves C_{aw} on L/λ ratio.

Table 3. Additional resistance coefficient in regular waves

<i>Froude number</i>	<i>Residual resistance coefficient</i>	<i>Residual resistance coefficient in calm water</i>	<i>Additional resistance coefficient in regular waves</i>	<i>Froude number</i>	<i>Residual resistance coefficient</i>	<i>Residual resistance coefficient in calm water</i>	<i>Additional resistance coefficient in regular waves</i>
<i>Fr</i>	C_r	$C_{rcw}(Fr)$	C_{aw}	<i>Fr</i>	C_r	$C_{rcw}(Fr)$	C_{aw}
$\lambda/L = 0.25$				$\lambda/L = 0.50$			
0.080	0.0011	1.850E-05	0.0010	0.071	0.0063	1.54E-06	0.0063
0.090	0.0011	6.416E-05	0.0011	0.098	0.0044	1.15E-04	0.0043
0.101	0.0012	1.425E-04	0.0010	0.118	0.0038	3.05E-04	0.0035
0.124	0.0013	3.798E-04	0.0009	0.134	0.0036	5.04E-04	0.0031
0.143	0.0014	6.134E-04	0.0008	0.152	0.0032	7.32E-04	0.0025
0.159	0.0015	8.313E-04	0.0007	0.165	0.0032	9.05E-04	0.0023
0.172	0.0017	9.944E-04	0.0007	0.180	0.0030	1.09E-03	0.0019
0.185	0.0018	1.146E-03	0.0007	-	-	-	-
0.197	0.0019	1.264E-03	0.0007	-	-	-	-
$\lambda/L = 0.625$				$\lambda/L = 0.75$			
0.067	0.0079	2.14E-06	0.0079	0.080	0.0123	1.850E-05	0.0123
0.089	0.0061	5.91E-05	0.0060	0.096	0.0108	1.011E-04	0.0107
0.108	0.0052	2.07E-04	0.0050	0.109	0.0098	2.126E-04	0.0096
0.126	0.0046	4.05E-04	0.0042	0.122	0.0089	3.534E-04	0.0085
0.142	0.0042	6.02E-04	0.0036	0.135	0.0080	5.173E-04	0.0075
0.157	0.0039	8.03E-04	0.0031	0.147	0.0075	6.680E-04	0.0069
0.168	0.0040	9.35E-04	0.0031	0.155	0.0072	7.727E-04	0.0065
-	-	-	-	0.167	0.0069	9.283E-04	0.0060

Conclusion

A study of the running qualities of the PV new generation has been carried out. These vessels differ from the old classical PV designs by the L/B ratio, by contours of the fore and end edges which are optimized using the CFD methods and are also designed taking into account usage of thrusters and full-turned rudder propellers.

The optimal model length for the ONMU towing tank was determined, which ensures the presence of self-similarity in terms of Reynolds numbers over the entire considered range of model speeds. Respectively the model scale of 1:47.5 was accepted. A model of PV140 passenger vessel was manufactured for testing.

Experimental tests of the running qualities of the mentioned model have been carried out in calm water and regular waves. The test results have been recalculated for a full-scale vessel using the standard method.

The dependences of additional resistance during the movement of the vessel in regular waves on different intensity and vessel's speed were constructed. The added resistance coefficient C_{aw} is too large in terms of residual resistance coefficient C_r ; at this stage of the research we cannot say whether this trend will continue for PV of other sizes; further researches are needed.

Comparing this study results with results of older methods leads us to Holtrop line. Feature of the Holtrop method is its reliance on model and trial test data for nearly 2000 vessels; its accuracy is believed to be in the order of 10%. Figures 18 and 19 show that at a design speed of 13 kn the difference between design and experimental data is about 20%. The stern shapes designed for angular propeller columns differ from those studied by Holtrop and Mennen [22, 23].

The obtained information was used to verify the correctness of the adopted design decisions and can be applied in the future in the case of developing similar vessel designs.

Here we are at the beginning of our way. It was intended to conduct a series of model tests and calculations for a range of hulls of mixed river-sea PV. The availability of such data would significantly simplify making valid design decisions at the initial stages of design.

Reference

- [1] G.V. Egorov, A.G. Egorov and I.A. Ilnytskyi. Design features of river-sea cruise passenger vessels for Russian inland waterways and adjacent seas. *Papers of the Intern. Conf. "Design & Operation of Passenger Ships"*, pages 21-29, Royal Institution of Naval Architects, London (UK), 2019.
- [2] G.V. Egorov and A.G. Egorov. River and river-sea cruise passenger ships. Operational experience, prognosis and novel concepts. *Proceedings of the Intern. Conf. "Sustainable and Safe Passenger Ships"*, pages 133-143, Royal Institution of Naval Architects & Hellenic Institute of Marine Technology, Athens (Greece), 2020.
- [3] G.V. Egorov, I.A. Ilnytskyi and Ya.V. Kalugin. Kruiznye passazhirskie suda smeshan-nogo (reka-more) plavaniya dlya rossiyskikh vnutrennikh vodnykh putey [Cruise passenger vessels of mixed river-sea navigation for Russian inland waterways, in Russian]. *Sc.-tech. collection of Russian Maritime Register of Shipping*, Issue 36, pages 255-276, RS, SPb, 2013.
- [4] V.I. Lyubimov. Osobennosti arkhitekturno-konstruktivnogo tipa sovremennykh rechnykh kruiznykh sudov [Features of architectural and structural type of modern river cruise ships, in Russian]. *Vestnik VGAVT. Section I: Shipbuilding, ship-repair and ecological safety of a vessel*, Issue 55, pages 49-55, VGAVT, Nizhny Novgorod, 2018.
- [5] A.A. Semin. Klassifikatsiya sposobov otsenki komfortabelnosti kak sostavlyashiy element proektirovaniya sudov i organizatsii obsluzhivaniya passazhirov [Classification of comfort assessment methods as a constituent element of ship design and passenger service organization, in Russian]. *Vestnik ONMU*, Issue. 1 (37), pages 180-187, ONMU, Odessa, 2013.
- [6] O. Zverkhovskiy and J.S. De Jong. DAMEN air cavity system of sustainable passenger ships. *Proceedings of the Intern. Conf. "Sustainable and Safe Passenger Ships"*, pages 65-70, Royal Institution of Naval Architects & Hellenic Institute of Marine Technology, Athens (Greece), 2020.
- [7] D.V. Kolesnik. Sravneniye obschey effektivnosti ispolzovaniya VRK i traditsionnogo propulsivnogo kompleksa na sudakh smeshannogo reka-more plavaniya [Comparison of overall efficiency of propeller steering columns and conventional propulsion on mixed river-sea going vessels, in Russian]. *Proceedings of the International Scientific-Practical Conference in honour of the 80th anniversary of Prof. V.V. Kozlyakov*, pages 131-136, Sudostroenie I sudoremont, Odessa, 2010.
- [8] VETH rudder propellers: *VETH propulsion by TwinDisc*. Papendrecht, The Netherlands, 2019.
- [9] SCHOTTEL propulsion for next-generation Yangtze cruise vessel. https://www.schottel.de/news-events/news/news-detail/?no_cache=1&tx_ttnews%5Btt_news%5D=645.
- [10] V.Ya. Bychkov, L.S. Grosheva and V.I. Pluschaeva. Matematicheskaya model sudna s kolesnym dvizhitelno-rulevym kompleksom «Zolotoe koltco» [Mathematical model of a vessel with wheeled propulsion-steering complex "Golden Ring", in Russian]. *Vestnik AGTU, Series: Marine technic and technology*, Issue 3, pages 36-49, AGTU, Astrakhan, 2018.
- [11] G.V. Egorov, I.A. Ilnytskyi, B.N. Stankov and A.A. Pechenuk. Prorabotka variantov propulsivnogo kompleksa sudna smeshannogo plavaniya classa «Volgo-Don max» [Development of variants of the propulsion unit for the mixed navigation vessel of the Volga-Don Max class]. *Morskoy vestnik*, Issue 2 (38), pages 101-106, 2011.
- [12] Issledovanie hodovykh kachestv passazhirskogo sudna na 300 passazhirov: tekhnicheskii otchet DMT-11-084. [Study of running abilities of 300 Passenger vessel: Technical report DMT-11-084, in Russian], Digital marine, 2011.
- [13] Issledovanie hodovykh kachestv passazhirskogo sudna na 150 passazhirov: tekhnicheskii otchet DMT-11-086. [Study of running abilities of 150 Passenger vessel: Technical report DMT-11-086, in Russian], Digital marine, 2011.
- [14] Issledovanie hodovykh kachestv passazhirskogo barzhe-buksirnogo sostava na 250 passazhirov: tekhnicheskii otchet DMT-11-088. [Study of running abilities of 250 Passenger tug-barge train: Technical report DMT-11-088, in Russian], Digital marine, 2011.

- [15] Issledovanie hodovykh kachestv passazhirskogo sudna: tekhnicheskiy otchet DMT-12-095. [Study of running abilities Passenger vessel: Technical report DMT-12-095, in Russian], Digital marine, 2012.
- [16] Trial performance prediction with open FP propellers: trial prediction of project ПС09. Rolls-Royce. 2014.
- [17] Program of full-scale sea trials for conditions of calculated wind-wave regime. *Volume MIB.5372*. Marine Engineering Bureau, Odessa, 2019.
- [18] Full-scale sea trials protocol for conditions of calculated wind-wave regime. *Volume MIB.5420*. Marine Engineering Bureau, Odessa, 2019.
- [19] O.V. Demidiuk. Modernizatsiya sistemy izmereniy opytovogo basseina ONMU. [Modernization of the measurement system of the towing tank of ONMU, in Russian]. *Vestnik ONMU*, Issue. 1 (34), pages 67-76, ONMU, Odessa, 2012.
- [20] O.V. Demidiuk, N.V. Efremova and A.V. Chernetskiy. O naznachenii harakteristik volneniya pri planirovanii eksperimentov v opytovom basseine ONMU. [Concerning wave characteristics acceptance during planning experiments in the towing tank of ONMU, in Russian] *Vestnik ONMU*, Issue. 3 (45), pages 145-156, ONMU, Odessa, 2015.
- [21] G.V. Egorov, V.I. Tonyuk, A.G. Egorov and O.V. Demidiuk. Features of the CV03 concept of floating transshipment complex with open cargo hold. *Proceedings of 18th International Congress of the International Maritime Association of the Mediterranean (IMAM 2019)*. Sustainable Development and Innovations in Marine Technologies, pages 338-345, Varna, Bulgaria, 2019.
- [22] J.A. Holtrop. Statistical reanalysis of resistance and propulsion data. *International Shipbuilding Progress*, 31, pages 272-276, 1984.
- [23] J.A. Holtrop and G.G.J. Mennen. An approximate power prediction method. *International Shipbuilding Progress*, 29, pages 166-170, 1982.
- [24] 1978 ITTC Performance Prediction Method. ITTC - *Recommended Procedures and Guidelines: 7.5 - 02 - 03 - 01.4. Revision 02*. ITTC, 2011
- [25] F.M. Katsman, A.F. Pustoshny and V.M. Shtumpf. Propulsivniye kachestva morskikh sudov [Propulsive qualities of seagoing ships in Russian]. *L.: Sudostroeniye*, 1972.
- [26] V.K. Turbal, V.S. Shpakov and V.M. Shtumpf. Proektirovaniye obvodov i dvizhiteley morskikh transportnykh sudov [Design of shapes and propulsion of marine transport vessels, in Russian]. *L.: Sudostroeniye*, 1983.